

CHARACTERISTICS OF RENAL DYSFUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE

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Abstract. *In patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, risk factors, comorbid conditions with impaired renal function have not been sufficiently studied and are currently considered an urgent problem. This article defines the importance of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease of the IV degree of severity of renal dysfunction in male patients, smokers, duration of the disease and concomitant diseases.*

Keywords: *chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, kidney dysfunction.*

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a significant medical and social issue in modern medicine due to its widespread prevalence among the population, high risk of disability and severe complications, and, in some cases, fatal outcomes. Globally, 2,8 million people lose their lives each year due to COPD. According to analytical forecasts by experts from the World Health Organization (WHO), by 2030, this disease will rank third as a cause of death, following cerebrovascular and cardiovascular diseases (1,5,8,19). In recent decades, COPD has been recognized not only as a respiratory disease but also as a condition manifesting systemic symptoms, primarily linked to systemic inflammation (6,21). Structural and functional changes in the respiratory system contribute to disruptions in homeostasis, cardiovascular issues, anemia, mineral metabolism in bone tissue, depressive-mental disorders, and kidney dysfunction (10,7,14,15,18).

According to several studies, kidney dysfunction is observed in 10.2% of COPD patients, the majority of whom are over 75 years old (11). Another study reported that chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and chronic kidney disease (CKD) co-occur in 20–53% of cases (12,14,3,4). It has been noted that in cases where these two diseases coexist and require hospitalization, mortality rates are higher. Some authors have highlighted that COPD patients frequently exhibit risk factors leading to CKD (1,2,5,7). These include elevated C-reactive protein levels (100%), smoking (92,0%), age over 65 (78,6%), and comorbid arterial hypertension (65,6%). Furthermore, the majority of COPD patients (92,6%) were found to have three or more risk factors (2). Another observation indicated that in addition to the mentioned risk factors, excessive body weight and obesity were reported in 49.6% of cases (8,20).

It is advisable to conduct scientific research focused on studying comorbid conditions, including kidney dysfunction, in patients with COPD.

Research Objective: To study kidney dysfunction in patients with stage IV of severe COPD.

Materials and Methods: The clinical and functional examinations of patients with stage IV of severe COPD were conducted in accordance with the latest international guidelines [Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) 2014 classification]. This research

involved a retrospective analysis of medical histories of 328 patients, aged 24 to 82 years, with stage IV of severe COPD who were hospitalized and treated at the Pulmonology Department of the Tashkent Medical Academy's Multidisciplinary Clinic from 2020 to 2023.

Of these patients, 236 (71.9±4.4%) were men, and 92 (28.0±5.5%) were women. The average age of the patients was 65.4±0.77 years (men: 66.6±1.18 years, women: 62.4±1.31 years), and the average disease duration was 15.2±1.08 years.

The patients were divided into two groups: Group 1 consisted of 45 patients with creatinine levels ≥115 mmol/L. Group 2 included 283 patients with creatinine levels ≤115 mmol/L. The distribution of COPD patients by age and gender is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Distribution of patients of stage IV of severe COPD by age and gender

Age group	COPD n=328				Total	
	Men		Women		Abs.	%
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%		
Up to 44 years	11	4,6±3,1	8	8,6±4,1	19	5,8±2,5
45-54	32	13,5±3,7	15	16,3±5,2	47	14,3±3,0
55-64	55	23,3±4,1	30	32,6±4,9	85	25,9±3,1
65-74	92	38,9±3,8	25	27,1±4,2	117	35,6±2,8
>74	46	19,4±2,1	14	15,2±1,8	63	19,2±1,5
Total	236	71,9±4,4	92	28,0±5,5	328	100

In all patients, kidney function was assessed by measuring creatinine levels in the blood and protein levels in the urine, body mass index (BMI), and oxygen saturation using pulse oximetry. Dyspnea in COPD was evaluated using the mMRC (Medical Research Council Dyspnea Scale).

Research Results: When kidney function was studied based on creatinine levels in patients with COPD, 13,8% showed elevated creatinine, and 66,4% had proteinuria. Changes in kidney function based on creatinine and proteinuria are presented in table 2.

In group 1, the average age of COPD patients was 68,2%, while in group 2, it was 66,1%. Gender-wise analysis showed that in group 1, 80% of the patients were men, and 67,4% were women.

In particular, it was found that in group 1, the majority of patients had higher levels of risk factors such as gender, disease duration, the number of smokers, ischemic heart disease (p<0,001), dyspnea severity (measured by mMRC scale, points), oxygen saturation based on the severity of respiratory failure (p<0,05), diabetes mellitus, gastrointestinal disorders, and nervous system disorders (p<0,05).

In group 1, the blood creatinine level was 183,7±20,0 mmol/l, while in group 2, it was 78,3±1,78 mmol/l (p<0,001). It is important to note that creatinine is a relatively variable indicator, influenced by factors such as patient age, gender, diet, and other variables.

The study results indicated that in patients with stage IV of severe COPD, when analyzing the association of risk factors with proteinuria, significant relationships were found with the following factors: **gender, smoking, disease duration, dyspnea severity, respiratory failure**

($p < 0,05$), **comorbidities** such as **anemia**, **urinary tract infections** ($p < 0,001$), **blood creatinine levels** were also found to be significantly associated with proteinuria (Table 3).

Table 2

Impact of risk factors on kidney function in patients with stage IV of severe COPD

Indicator	Creatinine ≥ 115 mmol/l n=45	Creatinine ≤ 114 mmol/l n=283	P
Average age	68,2±1,35	66,1±0,73	-
Men, n (%)	36 (80%)	191 (67,4%)	$p < 0,001$
Women, n (%)	8 (17,7%)	79 (27,9%)	$p < 0,001$
Smokers, n (%)	32 (71,1%)	151 (53,3%)	$P < 0,001$
Disease duration, years	14,4±2,1	11,4±3,4	$P < 0,05$
Body Mass Index (BMI), kg/m ²	24,9±0,90	27,6±0,49	$P < 0,05$
mMRC, Score	3,4±0,128	3,3±0,04	$P < 0,05$
SpO ₂ , n	89,3±0,126	91±0,126	$P < 0,05$
Ischemic Heart Disease, n (%)	29 (64,4 %)	218 (77,03%)	$P < 0,001$
Arterial Hypertension, n (%)	24 (53,3%)	153 (54,0%)	-
Diabetes Millitus, n (%)	9 (20%)	43 (15,1%)	$P < 0,05$
Anemia, n (%)	24 (53,3%)	133 (46,9%)	$P < 0,05$
Urinary Tract Infection, n (%)	12 (26,6%)	76 (26,8%)	-
Nervous System Disorders, n (%)	16 (35,5)	63 (22,2%)	$P < 0,05$
Gastrointestinal diseases, n (%)	14 (31,1%)	103 (36,3%)	$P < 0,05$
Creatinine, (mmol/l)	183,7±20,0	78,3±1,78	$P < 0,001$
Proteinuria, n (%)	37 (82,2%)	107 (37,8%)	$P < 0,001$

Table 3

Risk factor occurrence in relation to proteinuria in patients with stage IV of severe COPD

Indicator	Proteinuria present n=210	Proteinuria absent n=115	P
Average age	65,5±0,81	65,2±1,13	-
Men, n (%)	138 (65,7%)	86 (74,7%)	$p < 0,05$
Women, n (%)	64 (30,4%)	23 (20,0%)	$p < 0,05$
smokers, n (%)	131 (62,3%)	65 (56,5%)	$p < 0,05$
Disease duration, years	15,7±2,8	13,7±2,4	$p < 0,05$
Body mass index (BMI), кг/м ²	26,4±0,55	28,0±0,81	$p < 0,03$
mMRC, Score	3,55±0,05	3,0±0,075	$p < 0,05$
SpO ₂ , n	86,3±3,7	90,8±4,33	$p < 0,05$

Ischemic heart disease, n (%)	176 (83,8%)	81 (70,4)	p<0,05
Arterial hypertension, n (%)	117 (55,7%)	59 (51,3)	p<0,03
Diabetes millitus, n (%)	40 (19,0%)	24 (20,8)	-
Anemia, n (%)	110 (52,3%)	44 (38,2)	p<0,001
Urinary tract infection, n (%)	72 (34,2%)	14 (12,1)	p<0,001
Nervous system disorders, n (%)	57 (27,1%)	21 (18,2)	p<0,001
Gastrointestinal diseases, n (%)	66 (31,4%)	58 (50,4)	p<0,05
Creatinine, (mmol/l)	108,31±13,1	85,5±3,30	p<0,001
Proteinuria, n (%)	210 (64,0%)	115 (35%)	p<0,001

Conclusion: 1. In patients with stage IV of severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), an increase in creatinine and proteinuria levels was associated with male gender, smokers, ischemic heart disease (p<0,001), dyspnea severity (mMRC scale), oxygen saturation levels (p<0,05), disease duration, and comorbidities. These factors were found to significantly influence kidney dysfunction in COPD patients.

2. Although creatinine and proteinuria are important markers, they are not sufficient for diagnosing kidney dysfunction in COPD patients. Further in-depth investigations are necessary to establish a more comprehensive diagnostic approach.

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